

LABOR MARKET AND ENSURING THE BALANCE OF LABOR RESOURCES AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: The labor force is the main subject of the labor market. The gross domestic product created in the society is directly dependent not only on the material factors of production, but also on the factor of human capital, labor force. The state of labor resources in the labor market is related to socio-economic processes, and it is important to ensure the balance of resources.

Key words: labor force, labor resources, productivity of the labor force, human potential, active part of the labor force, reserve part of the labor force.

Аннотация: Рабочая сила является основным субъектом рынка труда. Создаваемый в обществе валовой внутренний продукт находится в прямой зависимости не только от материальных факторов производства, но и от фактора человеческого капитала, рабочей силы. Состояние трудовых ресурсов на рынке труда связано с социально-экономическими процессами, и важно обеспечить баланс ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: рабочая сила, трудовые ресурсы, производительность труда, человеческий потенциал, активная часть рабочей силы, резервная часть рабочей силы.

The main goal of the economic reforms carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to ensure economic stability, develop competitiveness in sectors and industries, and increase the level of social and economic well-being of the population.

It is worth noting that the level of economic well-being of the population is explained by several factors, such as the lifestyle of the country's population, the employment rate, the source of income, and the category of the labor force in the labor market is also important in the economy when such indicators are high.

Labor force resources are the part of the country's population that is able to work. These are: women aged 16 to 55 and men aged 16 to 60. In accordance with Article 77 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the age of employment is allowed from sixteen years. Children who have reached the age of fifteen are admitted to work with the written consent of one of their parents.

Two types of labor resources are distinguished:

The active part of the labor force is the persons engaged in social production.

The potential part of the labor force is those who are separated from production and are employed in temporary households.

How much wealth is created in society directly depends on the quantitative (number of people of working age) and quality (qualifications, skills, knowledge and experience) of the workforce.

The main elements of the structure of the labor market are the demand for labor force, the supply of labor force, the value and price of labor force, competition in hiring labor force. In the conditions of the market economy, it is important to ensure any economic balance, and the employment of the population in the labor market is considered as a specific economic balance. Ensuring balance in the labor market is necessarily explained by the balancing of labor demand and labor supply.

The high level of labor supply in the labor market is associated with the following socio-economic processes occurring in the country:

- natural population growth
- change of the economically inactive population (pupils, students, women, mothers with many children) who did not work and did not look for work to the economically active population;
- the emergence of employed people in the labor market as a result of the need for high-income jobs in the desire for additional income, and the addition of employed people to the unemployed population as a result of the loss of their jobs;
- manifestation of young people of working age as a labor force in the labor market;
- migratory movement of labor force, change of place of work or residence, etc.

The high level of labor demand in the labor market is directly related to the results and effectiveness of the economic and social reforms implemented by the state. There is an opportunity to increase the quality and quantity of economic benefits created by the state's support of entrepreneurs, the creation of privileges in the field of entrepreneurship, the strength of their legal guarantees, and the encouragement of entrepreneurs, as well as at the same time, such reforms in the field of entrepreneurship are also important in the creation of vacancies in the labor market.

It should be noted that during the reform of the economy of Uzbekistan, it became known that there are a number of problems in the labor market. One of these problems is the issue of distribution and redistribution of labor force. Providing employment to the population and its reformation is important for achieving economic stability. In accordance with the structural changes taking place in the country's economy, the directions of production also change. In this process, the management of the state is required in the distribution and redistribution of labor force.

In such cases, there is a need to use the means of distribution and redistribution of the idle or freed labor force as effectively as possible. On the contrary, there is a high probability that the labor force, which is not provided with a job according to its specialty, will go abroad in search of work and become labor migrants.

As it was mentioned above, the entrepreneurship sector, which is supported and encouraged in the country, is of great importance in the increase of the labor force demand in the country. Deepening of economic reforms, development of small business and private entrepreneurship is one of the main directions of economic reforms carried out in our republic. This requires the development of economic competition, the filling of the consumer market with goods and services, as well as the creation of a wide range of private entrepreneurs. Taking these into account, the following issues should be resolved in the Republic today:

- bringing broad sections of the population into market activities, eliminating the psychology of consumerism in them, arousing the desire of the population to actively engage in private entrepreneurship, small business activities;

- fundamental renewal of economic relations in agriculture;

- to further develop the activities of farmers and farms and increase their number as much as possible, to provide temporary unemployed people with additional jobs by establishing small enterprises in the regions;

- to accelerate the development of market relations and infrastructure in the regions, to create conditions for strengthening active economic competition.

Today a number of reliefs have been created regarding the issues of registration of business entities in Uzbekistan. In particular, with the help of digitized technologies, entities are being registered through electronic government tools, my.gov.uz networks, without excessive waiting. A number of reforms to reform and improve the business sector are being implemented in our republic. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to fundamentally improve the quality and scope of state control in the field of business" aims to further improve the business environment by fundamentally improving state control, and the following are the priority directions for reforming state control in the field:

- optimization of functions related to control of activities that do not harm the rights and legal interests of citizens, health, public and state security, and introduction of mechanisms to prevent the implementation of ineffective control functions;

- introduction of the "smart control" model with extensive use of information technologies, digitization of all information and processes related to the field, implementation of state control using the "risk analysis" system as a priority in the "electronic inspector" method;

- introduction of the standard of prevention of violations, establishment of mechanisms for encouraging compliance with the mandatory requirements provided for in regulatory and legal documents;

- ensuring the openness and publicity of information related to the implementation of state control, prevention of corruption, conflict of interests, as well as cases of selective application of norms of regulatory and legal documents;

- setting special requirements for officials to have sufficient knowledge, skills and abilities to ensure legality in the implementation of state control.

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